

Untying the anchor for the lipopolysaccharide: lipid A structural modification systems offer diagnostic and therapeutic options to tackle polymyxin resistance

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Polymyxin antibiotics are the last resort for treating patients in intensive care units infected with multiple-resistant Gram-negative bacteria. Due to their polycationic structure, their mode of action is based on an ionic interaction with the negatively charged lipid A portion of the lipopolysaccharide (LPS). The most prevalent polymyxin resistance mechanisms involve covalent modifications of lipid A: addition of the cationic sugar 4-amino-L-arabinose (L-Ara4N) and/or phosphoethanolamine (pEtN). The modified structure of lipid A has a lower net negative charge, leading to the repulsion of polymyxins and bacterial resistance to membrane disruption. Genes encoding the enzymatic systems involved in these modifications can be transferred either through chromosomes or mobile genetic elements. Therefore, new approaches to resistance diagnostics have been developed. On another note, interfering with these enzymatic systems might offer new therapeutic targets for drug discovery. This literature review focuses on diagnostic approaches based on structural changes in lipid A and on the therapeutic potential of molecules interfering with these changes.

KEY WORDS: antimicrobial resistance; adjuvants; Gram-negative bacteria; MALDI-TOF-MS; MCR-1

Polymyxin B and polymyxin E (colistin) are cationic cyclic lipodecapeptide antibiotics that disrupt the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria by displacing divalent cations Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} and enabling their interaction with the negatively charged phosphate moieties of lipid A (1), the so-called anchor of the lipopolysaccharide (LPS). This interaction destabilises the LPS, increases the permeability of the bacterial membrane, leads to the leakage of the cytoplasmic content, and eventually kills the bacteria (2). Polymyxins were discovered in 1947 (3) as secondary metabolites isolated from the soil bacterium *Bacillus polymyxa*. A decade later, polymyxins were abandoned in clinical practice due to high nephrotoxicity and neurotoxicity and replaced by the emerging less toxic antibiotics (1, 4).

Today, polymyxins are used as last-resort agents in human medicine to treat infections which are caused by Gram-negative bacteria resistant to all other available antibiotics (5). Therefore, the emerging resistance to this last-resort treatment is one of the gravest public health concerns, as it leaves no reliable treatment options for patients in intensive care units.

The most prevalent form of polymyxin resistance is through structural modifications of lipid A, a polyanionic segment of the LPS. The two most common modifications include the addition of the cationic sugar 4-amino-L-arabinose (L-Ara4N) and/or phosphoethanolamine (pEtN), as presented in Figure 1. The modified structure of lipid A has a decreased net negative charge, which leads to the repulsion of colistin and protects bacteria from

membrane disruption (6, 7). These lipid A structural changes follow distinct mechanisms for plasmid- and chromosome-encoded resistance. Moreover, lipid A structures are species-specific. Polymyxin resistance is intrinsic for some bacterial species such as *Proteus* spp., *Burkholderia* spp., *Serratia* spp. (8), and *Moraxella* spp. (9), because their lipid A structure has a lower net negative charge anyway. Other Gram-negative bacteria acquire polymyxin resistance either through plasmid- or chromosome-encoded genes.

Chromosome-encoded resistance is based on the mutation of genes coding for lipid A. The genes which are involved in lipid A biosynthesis are upregulated by the PmrA/PmrB, PhoP/PhoQ, and CrrA/CrrB two-component systems (TCS) or mutations of the *mgrB* gene (7). Genes under TCS control induce *eptA* and *arn* operon members (e.g. *arnT*) required for lipid A modifications (10–12). ArnT transfers L-Ara4N, and EptA adds pEtN moieties to the phosphate groups of lipid A (7, 13–15).

Plasmid-encoded resistance enables horizontal transfer of *mcr* genes, which code for enzymes that transfer pEtN onto the phosphate groups of the lipid A. So far, 10 classes of *mcr* genes have been identified (*mcr*-1 to *mcr*-10) (6, 16–24).

Other mechanisms which contribute to polymyxin resistance in synergy with lipid A modification systems include the expression of efflux pumps, capsule formation, and overexpression of the OprH, an outer membrane protein (25, 26).

Figure 1 The two most common types of lipid A modifications that lead to colistin resistance

Regardless of the mechanism, polymyxin resistance raises the greatest global concern in all aspects of the One Health paradigm (an interdisciplinary approach that balances the health of people, animals, and the environment): polymyxin-resistant bacteria have been found in environment-, veterinary medicine-, and human medicine-related bacterial strains (27). Although methods for the detection of lipid A structural modifications have mainly been developed for use in human medicine clinical diagnostics, these principles apply for the detection of environmental and veterinary medicine polymyxin-resistant strains. In addition, drugs which may arise from future research could also be utilised in veterinary medicine. The One Health approach to combat polymyxin resistance will be crucial, as one influences the other. For instance, the first *mcr-1* positive bacterial strain has been found in 2016 in China in pigs and later in other food animals (6). Therefore, although it started from veterinary medicine, now *mcr*-positive strains can be found in both human medicine and environmental bacteria.

Although current polymyxin resistance is less frequent than resistance of other classes of antibiotics, we expect an increase in both human and veterinary medicine in the years to come. In this review article we will focus on current potential use of lipid A for clinical diagnostics of resistance and adjuvant therapy.

Lipid A structural analysis in clinical diagnostics

Currently, the gold standard recommended by the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) for clinical diagnostics of polymyxin resistance used in clinical microbiology laboratories is minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) (28). Although these diagnostic methods are the most reliable at the moment, they do not inform about the resistance mechanism involved. In clinical settings, this mechanism is generally interpreted through polymerase chain reaction (PCR) after phenotypic resistance has been established (7). Studies have shown that some bacterial strains, referred to as polymyxin heteroresistant, do not show resistance in MIC susceptibility testing but do acquire lipid A modifications along with the genes for polymyxin resistance (29–35). These strains raise concern over their potential to spread polymyxin

resistance in clinics, as they usually are not tested for genetic polymyxin resistance. Yet, information about the exact polymyxin resistance mechanism that a bacterium has developed can help us decide the course of hospital treatment. For instance, a patient infected with a bacterium that has plasmid-encoded polymyxin resistance may require quarantine and more cautious behaviour of clinical staff. This is because plasmids can be transferred horizontally from one bacterial species to another. Bacteria that have colonised a hospital area and clinical staff might receive genes for polymyxin resistance by being in close contact with a patient infected by a bacterium carrying plasmid-encoded polymyxin resistance.

Researchers have been working on developing rapid clinical microbiology diagnostic assays which rely on the mass spectrometry (MS) of lipid A structural modifications. Prior to analysis, these bacterial samples require specific treatment to cleave a ketosidic bond in the LPS to release lipid A.

Clinical microbiology laboratories have increasingly been utilising matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionisation – time of flight – mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF-MS) to identify microbes based on protein profiling. This includes profiling for lipid A structures to develop assays that rapidly determine mechanisms underlying polymyxin resistance in clinical settings (36–44). Molecules analysed by MALDI-TOF-MS need to be ionised prior to separation. Negative ionisation mode is optimal for lipid A because its phosphate groups can easily be ionised into anionic form. In view of the fact that lipid A structures are species-specific, the findings of MS analysis need to be interpreted carefully and individually. To illustrate the rationale of lipid A analysis for clinical diagnostics, we will show examples of lipid A structural modifications for some bacterial species which can be visualised by MALDI-TOF-MS.

Klebsiella pneumoniae has at least four native lipid A structures, which have the MS spectrum m/z values of 1824, 1840, 2063, and 2078 (37, 41, 45). Depending on the mechanism underlying polymyxin resistance, there can be an addition of L-Ara4N or/and pEtN, in which case the m/z values increase by +131 or +123, respectively. The same rationale in structural modifications has been observed in other Gram-negative bacteria. Therefore, chromosome-

encoded resistance can be viewed as lipid A m/z values of 1971 and 2209, plasmid-encoded resistance can be viewed as lipid A m/z values of 1963 and 2201, and, if both mechanisms are involved, as lipid A m/z values of 1963, 2201, and 2209 (37, 41). Table 1 shows the proposed structures of native and modified lipid A for *K. pneumoniae*.

As for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, there is no evidence of pEtN addition to lipid A. What we know for now is that the acquired resistance arises from the addition of one or two L-Ara4N moieties to position 1 and/or 4' phosphate in the native lipid A (39). The most common native lipid A structures can be viewed as m/z values of 1446 and 1462. Therefore, chromosome-encoded resistance can be viewed as lipid A m/z values of 1577, 1593, 1708, and 1724 (39). Table 2 shows the proposed structures of native and modified lipid A for *P. aeruginosa*.

Native lipid A structures of *Acinetobacter baumannii* have m/z values of 1728 and 1910. Chromosome-encoded resistance is based on a 4' pEtN addition to lipid A and a +123 shift (38). Table 3 shows the proposed structures (38, 41). Some minor native lipid A peaks include tetraacylated and pentaacylated lipid A with m/z values of 1404 and 1530, respectively (these structures are not included in this review). Plasmid-encoded resistance has not been detected in *A. baumannii* yet.

The most common *Escherichia coli* native lipid A structure has the m/z value of 1796. Chromosome-encoded resistance is identified at m/z of 1927 (L-Ara4N), plasmid-encoded resistance at m/z of 1919, and both mechanisms at respective m/z values of 1919 and 1927 (40, 46). Table 4 shows the proposed structures (40, 41, 46).

Salmonella enterica has at least five native lipid A structures, which correspond to m/z values of 1796, 1812, 1876, 2034, and 2050 (Table 5). Chromosome-encoded resistance is identified as lipid A m/z values of 1927 and 2165 (corresponding to the L-Ara4N addition), and plasmid-encoded resistance as lipid A m/z values of 1919, 1935, 2157, and 2173 (corresponding to the pEtN addition) (36, 41).

Based on the findings from the Larrouy-Maumus research group at Imperial College London, the MALDIxin test, commercialised by Bruker Corporation under the name MBT Lipid Xtract™ kit (47), shows great promise as indicator of polymyxin resistance to be used in clinical diagnostics.

Promising targets in lipid A structural modification systems for adjuvant polymyxin treatment

Currently, polymyxins are the most promising agents for treating infections with extensively drug-resistant (XDR) Gram-negative bacteria. Therefore, we need to foresightedly work on polymyxin adjuvant therapeutics. Adjuvant compounds normally lack inherent antimicrobial activity as single agents, but in combination with a specific antibiotic they potentiate its effects. The idea of polymyxin adjuvant therapy is to reverse polymyxin resistance by inhibiting

one of the resistance-driving mechanisms (mechanisms involved in lipid A modifications). Some of the most promising targets include enzymes involved in lipid A modification systems responsible for resistance [e.g. MCR-1, ArnT and diacylglycerol kinase A (DgkA)]. The interactions of colistin with lipid model membranes have been described thoroughly by structural biology studies (48), which have shown how these interactions change when pEtN is added to the phosphate groups of lipid A (49, 50) and how changes in LPS charge renders polymyxins ineffective. Therefore, in theory, for polymyxins to regain their efficacy these changes need to be prevented. In this context, we see another potential application of MALDI-TOF-based polymyxin resistance screening. For instance, analysing lipid A structure would indicate which inhibitor class would be useful for each patient.

MCR-1 is a pEtN transferase encoded by plasmid-borne *mcr-1* genes. Xu et al. (51) have evidenced that MCR-1 [expressed, purified, and incubated with a natural substrate mimetic (nitrobenzodiazole-labelled glycerol-3-pEtN)] transfers pEtN to phosphate groups of lipid A in Gram-negative bacteria, while nitrobenzodiazole-glycerol is released. The structure of MCR-1 soluble C-terminal domain has been elucidated through X-ray crystallography (52–56). Its active site is located in the soluble domain, coordinated by an essential Zn^{2+} ion, and has a highly conserved (through the pEtN family) T285 amino acid residue that acts as a catalytic nucleophile in substrate modifications (52, 57, 58). These findings provide valuable starting point for computer-aided drug design (CADD) in the quest for novel MCR-1 inhibitors (59, 60). Since the discovery of MCR-1, some research groups have been screening for potential MCR-1 inhibitors from natural products (61–66) or developing *de novo* synthesised MCR-1 inhibitors (67). Interestingly, an FDA-approved drug, auranofin (used in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis), has also shown MCR-1 inhibition (68). So far, this is the most studied lipid A-related target for potential adjuvants. As MCR-1 has been studied quite extensively, there is hope that these findings can be applied to other members of the MCR family. It would be ideal that a candidate drug inhibits all members of the MCR protein family.

As for chromosome-encoded polymyxin resistance, small molecules that downregulate TCS have been found to reverse resistance (69, 70). Another promising target related to chromosome-encoded resistance is ArnT. Ghirga et al. (71) performed a virtual screening for ArnT inhibitors to discover a potent colistin adjuvant BBN149, which can be used as a lead molecule for further development. Quaglio et al. (72) have shown that ent-Beyerane diterpenes inhibit ArnT thanks to their resemblance to L-Ara4N. This means that the structure of these compounds most likely has a similar binding mode as L-Ara4N. Another target which might be of interest is DgkA. As mentioned above, EptA is transferring pEtN to the phosphate groups of lipid A. EptA uses phosphatidylethanolamine (PE) as its pEtN donor, which results in the formation of diacylglycerol (DAG) as a by-product (10). DAG is quickly phosphorylated by DgkA into phosphatidic acid, a precursor for PE synthesis (73), and DAG accumulation has been

Table 1 *K. pneumoniae* native and modified lipid A structures and their corresponding m/z values (35, 39)

<i>K. pneumoniae</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structures
	1824	
Native lipid A	1840	

Table 1 continued

<i>K. pneumoniae</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structures
	2062	
Native lipid A	2078	

Table 1 continued

<i>K. pneumoniae</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structures
Chromosome-encoded resistance – L-Ara4N addition	1971 (1840 + 131)	
	2209 (2078 + 131)	

Table 1 continued

<i>K. pneumoniae</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structures
	1963 (1840 + 123)	
Plasmid-encoded resistance – pEtN addition	2201 (2078 + 123)	

Table 2 *P. aeruginosa* native and modified lipid A structures and their corresponding m/z values (37)

<i>P. aeruginosa</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
	1446	
Native lipid A	1462	

Table 2 continued

<i>P. aeruginosa</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
	1577 (1446 + 131)	
Chromosome-encoded resistance – L-Ara4N addition	1593 (1462 + 131)	
	1708 (1446 + 262)	

Table 2 continued

<i>P. aeruginosa</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
Chromosome-encoded resistance – L-Ara4N addition	1724 (1462 + 262)	

Table 3 *A. baumannii* native and modified lipid A structures and their corresponding m/z values (36, 39)

<i>A. baumannii</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
Native lipid A	1728	

Table 3 continued

<i>A. baumannii</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
Native lipid A	1910	
Chromosome-encoded resistance – pEtN addition	2033 (1910 + 123)	

Table 4 *E. coli* native and modified lipid A structures and their corresponding m/z value (38, 39, 44)

<i>E. coli</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
Native lipid A	1796	
Chromosome-encoded resistance – L-Ara4N addition	1927 (1796 + 131)	

Table 4 continued

<i>E. coli</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
Both plasmid- and chromosome- encoded resistance	1919 (1796 + 123)	

Table 5 *S. enterica* native and modified lipid A structures and their corresponding m/z values (34, 39)

<i>S. enterica</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
	1796	
Native lipid A	1812	

Table 5 continued

<i>S. enterica</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
Native lipid A	1876	
	2034	

Table 5 continued

<i>S. enterica</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
Native lipid A	2050	
Chromosome-encoded resistance – L-Ara4N addition	1927 (1796 + 131)	

Table 5 continued

<i>S. enterica</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
Chromosome-encoded resistance – L-Ara4N addition	2165 (2034 + 131)	
Plasmid-encoded resistance – pEtN addition	1919 (1796 + 123)	

Table 5 continued

<i>S. enterica</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
	1935 (1812 + 123)	
Plasmid-encoded resistance – pEtN addition	2157 (2034 + 123)	

Table 5 continued

<i>S. enterica</i>		
Type	m/z	Proposed structure
Plasmid-encoded resistance – pEtN addition	2173 (2050 + 123)	

shown to inhibit EptA activity (15, 74). All this points to DgkA as a prominent target of polymyxin resistance adjuvant therapy.

Another potential option are eukaryotic kinase inhibitors, which have been found to re-sensitise bacteria resistant to colistin. Although the mechanism is not clear yet, they have been reported to lower the rate of lipid A modifications by L-Ara4N and pEtN (75). Sertraline, an FDA-approved selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI) used for the treatment of depression, has been found to revert polymyxin resistance, as it seems to interfere with the *eptA* lipid A modification pathway (76).

All things considered, there is immense potential for the development of polymyxin adjuvants by targeting lipid A modification systems.

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Odvezivanje sidra lipopolisaharida: sustavi za strukturne modifikacije lipida A nude dijagnostičke i terapijske opcije za borbu protiv polimiksinse rezistencije

Polimiksinški antibiotici zadnja su linija liječenja pacijenata u intenzivnim jedinicama liječenja koji su inficirani multiplorezistentnim gram-negativnim bakterijama. S obzirom na njihovu polikationsku strukturu, njihov mehanizam djelovanja temelji se na ionskoj interakciji s negativno nabijenim dijelom lipopolisaharida koji se naziva lipid A. Najčešći mehanizmi rezistencije na polimiksine uključuju kovalentne modifikacije lipida A: adiciju kationskog šećera 4-amino-L-arabinoze (L-Ara4N) i/ili fosfoetanolamina (pEtN). Modificirana struktura lipida A sadrži niži neto negativni naboj, što prouzrokuje odbojne sile između polimiksina i lipida A. To dovodi do bakterijske rezistencije na urušavanje integriteta stanične membrane. Geni koji kodiraju za enzimske sustave koji sudjeluju u navedenim modifikacijama mogu se prenositi kromosomima ili mobilnim genskim elementima. Stoga su i razvijeni novi pristupi dijagnostici rezistencije. Osim toga, u navedenim enzimskim sustavima postoje i moguće nove terapijske mete za razvoj lijekova. Ovaj pregledni rad usredotočuje se na dijagnostičke metode koje se temelje na strukturnim promjenama u lipidu A i na terapijskom potencijalu molekula koje interferiraju s navedenim strukturnim modifikacijama.

KLJUČNE RIJEČI: antimikrobna rezistencija; adjuvansi; gram-negativne bakterije; MALDI-TOF-MS; MCR-1